

FABRICATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE FIBER NANOCOMPOSITE

Seong Woo Ryu, Jae Won Hwang and Soon Hyung Hong*

Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology,
291 Daehak-ro, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon 305-701, Korea

* Prof. Soon Hyung Hong (shhong@kaist.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Carbon nanotube, Forest, Fiber, Nanocomposite, Dry spinning, Strength*

1. Introduction

Carbon nanotubes(CNTs) are increasingly attracting scientific and technological interest due to their significant advantages over most existing materials. Many researchers have shown that CNTs possess remarkable mechanical[1], thermal[2], and exceptionally high elastic properties[3]. However, the application of CNTs as nano-sized tubular form makes it difficult to utilize those outstanding properties in bulk scale[4]. In order to use CNTs as structural materials in the construction of high performance structures such as space shuttle, bulletproof jacket and electronic textile, the CNTs should be in their fiber form where the single nanotubes are highly aligned and packed in an arrangement. Therefore, emerging technique for utilizing CNTs to practical application is fiber spinning. Researchers have attempted to fabricate CNT fibers which minimize defects to achieve unique properties of CNTs in bulk scale[5]. There has been a substantial amount of research on the fabrication of neat CNT fibers based on the two major strategies: solution spinning[6-8], and solid-state spinning[9-19]. To acquire maximized mechanical properties of CNT fibers, both strategies require effective post-processing techniques such as twisting[15], surface-tension-driven densification[16], and solution infiltration [15-18]. However, the post-processing techniques have only been provided passive ways to improve the properties using additional weak interactions and morphological changes. In this study has been investigated to

fabricate super-strong CNT fiber nano composite.

2. Experimental Procedures

Vertically aligned CNT arrays were synthesized by thermal CVD process. The thickness of catalysts used in this paper were Al(10nm)/Fe(1nm to 5nm) on Si wafer. The Al layer and Fe layer is deposited on Si wafer by sputtering. Forming gas such as argon(Ar) gas, hydrogen(H₂) gas and oxygen(O₂) gas was used as carrier gas, and ethylene(C₂H₄) gas was used as carbon source. For the growth of CNT array, temperature is heated up to 750°C for 10 minute within the flowing 2000sccm Ar gas. Then, 60sccm H₂ gas was added to Ar gas for 5 min. Finally, 1000sccm C₂H₄ gas and 1sccm O₂ gas were added to Ar gas and H₂ gas for 20 minute.

CNT fiber is directly spun from CNT array with spindle rotation rate of 1000rpm and drawing rate of 10cm/min and densified with ethanol and 10wt% polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) dissolved solution. Scanning electron microscopy (XL30SFEG Philips) and transmission electron microscopy (JEM-3010, JEOL) are used to analyse their morphologies and of CNT fibers. Tensile test is carried out to measure mechanical properties of CNT fiber by micro-force testing system (Instron 8848, Instron).

3. Results and Discussion

By using thermal chemical vapor deposition(CVD), synthesis of vertically aligned

CNT array has been researched widely for spinning of fibers. The spun fibers from vertically aligned CNT array performed low density and excellent mechanical properties with over 99% were fabricated. CNT forest with length of 583 μm were synthesized on 1nm to 5nm thickness of Fe catalyst layer and 10nm thick Al buffer layer by using thermal CVD (Fig. 2a, b). CNT fibers were directly spun from CNT forest (Fig.1) and post treated with twisting, surface-tension-driven densification by ethanol. During the densification, 10 wt.% PVA dissolved solution was used to infiltrate linker molecules for densification of CNT fibers. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) image shows as drawn CNT fiber (Fig. 2c) and CNT fiber after post treatment (Fig. 2d). Various catalyst substrate (1nm, 3nm and 5nm thickness Fe layer) has been prepared to control morphology of each CNT forest. CNT forest is successfully synthesized. On the other hand, CNT fiber is only spun from catalyst condition

Fig.1 (a) schematic illustration of dry spinning process and (b) SEM image of spinning carbon nanotube fibers from the forest.

Fig.2 SEM images of vertically aligned CNT arrays after (a) 20 minute synthesized,(b) its high resolution SEM image. (c) as drawn CNT fiber from CNT forest and (d) CNT fiber after post spinning process such as twisting, densification, and infiltration.

of 1nm Fe substrate. Thicker Fe catalyst leads to synthesize thicker CNTs with numerous walls

and this leads to interfere continuous bundling between CNTs. Histogram in Fig. 3 shows distribution of CNT forest.

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As drawn CNT fibers from the forest by Van der Waals interaction is in aero-gel state with cavities inside. Loosely packed CNT fiber shows strength of under 100MPa. Surface tension driven densification process and twisting process increase packing density of CNT fibers. Main aim of these post spinning process is to improve inter nanotube contacts. As a result, both strength and elongation has been increased. Finally, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was infiltrated to CNT fibers (Fig. 4) as binders. PVA has been used as a basic supporting material for both solution state spun and solid state spun CNT

Fig. 3 Histogram of wall and diameter distribution and its TEM image. (a) CNT forest synthesized on deposition of 1nm thick Fe, (b) 3nm thick Fe and (c) 5nm thick Fe.

fibers because of its high tensile strength, high flexibility, high adhesive properties and emulsifying properties. As a result, PVA-infiltrated CNT fiber performed higher strength

with a lower strain-to-failure (Fig. 4). PVA is basically atactic materials but because of hydrogen bonding of its hydroxyl groups, PVA support and enhance bonding strength between CNT bundles.

Fig. 4 Stress-strain curves of various CNT fibers. (a) Aero gel CNT fibers directly spun from forest, (b) after ethanol densification CNT fiber, (c) after twisting and densification CNT fiber and (d) PVA infiltrated CNT fiber.

4. Conclusions

Direct spinning process of CNT fiber from the vertically aligned forest was investigated. By controlling of catalyst morphology, various CNT (double wall to several multiwall) forest is synthesized for fiber spinning. With post spinning, CNTs are densely packed and strongly linked by their own bundling phenomenon. Supporting of PVA binders, CNT fiber performed maximum strength of over 1 GPa. The proposed CNT fibers have high potential as ultra-light strength structural materials for future applications such as .

5. Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the financial supports from 'Center for Nanostructured Materials Technology' under '21st Century Frontier R&D Programs' of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (2010K000275).

6. References

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